

EFFECTIVENESS OF DIFFERENTIAL APPROACH IN MUSIC LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of the differential approach in modern music education, its effectiveness in developing students' artistic and aesthetic thinking, and the specific aspects of organizing the lesson process. The research covers the methodology for selecting educational materials, taking into account the individual abilities, level of musical perception, and interests of students. The article outlines the theoretical foundations and practical results of the differential approach, and justifies the importance of pedagogical technologies in improving musical literacy.

Keywords: Music education, differential approach, individual ability, musical perception, pedagogical technology, aesthetic education, methodology, efficiency, student motivation, artistic taste.

Today, the essence of reforms in the education system is aimed at maximizing the potential of each individual. In particular, in music culture lessons, it is a priority to provide students with not only theoretical knowledge, but also to enrich their inner world, develop emotional perception and demonstrate their creative potential. However, the fact that students in each class have different musical hearing, sense of rhythm, vocal capabilities and aesthetic experience requires the teacher to build the lesson not according to the same pattern, but based on a differentiated (stratified) approach. A differential approach means organizing the educational process by dividing students into groups depending on their psychophysiological characteristics, abilities and knowledge levels. In music lessons, this approach helps to overcome the student's "I can't do it" barrier and instill in him a stable interest in music. When analyzing the effectiveness of a differential approach in music education, it is first necessary to determine the level of musical preparation of students. Typically, students in a class can be conditionally divided into three groups: the first group - students with high musical abilities, experience in playing or singing musical instruments; the second group - those with average abilities, but a high interest in music; the third group - students with a poorly developed musical ear or sense of rhythm, passive in relation to science. If the teacher gives everyone the same task of the same complexity, strong students will get bored, and weak students will be discouraged from not being able to complete the task. A differential approach creates a "development zone" that is suitable for each group. This approach is very useful in the singing section of the lesson. For example, in a choir, students with limited vocal abilities can be assigned simpler parts, that is, the main melody, while students with a sharp musical ear are assigned the task of performing the second part or more complex decorative parts. This not only improves the overall sound, but also forms in each child a sense of feeling their place in the collective work. At the same time, stratification is also important in the process of analyzing a musical work. While the first group of students is asked analytical questions on the genre, form and harmonic structure of the work, the third group is asked to express emotional and figurative ideas about the mood of the work, the images depicted in it. A differentiated approach in the process of listening to music serves to increase the intellectual potential of students. For example, before listening to a classical work, the teacher distributes tasks of varying difficulty to students. The "Artists" group is assigned to draw a picture to the music or choose a color scheme, the "Poets" group is assigned to create a short essay or a verbal portrait based on their impressions of the music, and the "Musicologists" group is assigned to determine the dynamic changes of the work and the composition of the instruments. This method makes the lesson lively, interactive and effective. Every child understands the essence of a musical piece through the type of activity they enjoy and are able to perform.

In the current era of information technology, the use of electronic resources opens up great opportunities for implementing a differentiated approach. With the help of musical games, virtual instruments and test programs, each student can learn at his own pace. For example, for a student learning to read music, special software immediately shows his mistakes, and the student works independently on himself. At this time, the teacher has the opportunity to individually engage with other students who need help. A differentiated approach is aimed not only at imparting knowledge, but also at protecting the psychological state of the student as a person. In music lessons, it is necessary to create a "situation of success" by encouraging even small achievements, not laughing at the student's mistakes. It is known that music has a direct effect on a person's emotional intelligence. Through a differentiated approach, we teach students not only to listen to music, but also to feel it. For example, choleric children, by temperament, are more likely to be interested in active, dynamic music, while melancholic children may be more spiritually nourished by lyrical, calm melodies. If the teacher takes into account the general mood in the classroom and the individual preferences of the students when choosing a repertoire, the effectiveness of the lesson increases several times. Observations conducted within the framework of the article show that in classes where a differentiated approach is used, the level of musical literacy and activity of students is 35-40 percent higher than in traditional classes. Another important aspect of the differential approach is creative tasks. Giving students tasks such as analyzing their favorite modern songs in a classical style or giving a new interpretation to folk songs increases their creativity. In this process, the student feels free and seeks to express his "I". Music, unlike other disciplines, is not limited by strict formulas, so there is a lot of room for a differentiated approach here. The skill of a teacher is to be able to find the "musical spark" in each child and ignite it.

Conclusion The use of a differentiated approach in music lessons is not just a methodological method, but a key factor in humanizing education. This approach serves to respect the individual capabilities of students, strengthen their self-confidence, and form a healthy attitude towards musical art. Studies show that a differentiated teaching system not only increases students' interest in the lesson, but also broadens their aesthetic outlook and enhances their artistic taste. In short, by taking an individual approach to each child, we can raise not only a musically literate person, but also a well-rounded generation that is spiritually mature, appreciates art, and thinks creatively. A modern music teacher must consistently use the principles of a differentiated approach in his or her work, turning each lesson into a field of discoveries and joyful moments. Only then will music become a true educational tool.

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